

[v1 - August 12, 2024]

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Risk Response

Adversarial Discourse Game

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Summary

Risk Response is a card game developed by Max Willis and Greta Adamo to explore concepts of risk, impact, mitigation and adaptation, in relation to future climate change, societal and technological factors. The game relies on common knowledge of risks faced by humanity, now and in the future (e.g. extreme temperatures and rising sea levels associated with climate change, or financial loss and social instability arising from cybersecurity problems). Risk Response can be played by non-experts, and makes visible through gameplay how synergies between multiple human responses to anticipated risks can help to overcome adversity. However it also shows how multiple risks can cascade into seemingly insurmountable challenges for the future of human (and ecosystem) health and safety and sustainable development. The game allows for modification and extensions to accommodate domain experts to examine and debate specific risks and responses. Gameplay revolves around teams taking turns to propose future risks and debate the viability of possible responses, using an augmented “futures cone” to collectively determine the plausibility, or possibility of overcoming risks and managing impacts. An extended version of gameplay includes collaborative modeling activities to further elaborate and discuss risk concepts.

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Left: Risk Response cards. Right: collaborative modeling activity.

The game

Risk Response consists of three sets of cards, beginning with **Risk or Impact** cards, which suggest potential risks to humanity. These cards present various rubrics such as *Water, Air, Ocean* and *Food*, with suggestions for players to choose from, or propose their own. The second set comprises **Mitigate or Adapt** cards (i.e. responses), which present rubrics for human responses, for example *Society, Technology, Built Environment* and *Government*. The third set are **discourse wildcards**, which can aid (or sabotage) group discussion, such as *Catastrophe, Stroke of Luck*, and *Anticipation*. A modified “futures cone” (after Voros [6]) is used to guide gameplay conversation.

Risk or Impact, Mitigate or Adapt and discourse wildcard.

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The rules

Players divide themselves into two teams, **Team Risk** and **Team Humanity**.

The cards are separated into groups according to the three types and shuffled.

Team Risk draws ONE **Risk or Impact** card, and together players decide on a risk or impact for humanity. **Team Risk** is instructed to play impassively, to simulate data driven risk prediction.

Each player from **Team Humanity** draws ONE **Mitigate or Adapt** card.

When **Team Risk** proposes their risk or impact, **Team Humanity** nominates TWO PLAYERS to propose a response to the risk. **Team Humanity** is encouraged to impassioned play, to stimulate innovation.

Each player, and spectators who opt in, draws ONE **discourse wildcard**, which can be played at any time.

When the risks and responses have been proposed, the two teams and spectators must debate the possible future which has been presented. **Team Humanity** must convince everyone that their response is plausible, for the chance to win the round.

During the discussion phase of the game, spectators are encouraged to add their voices to the game.

Collaborative modeling game extension

To stimulate discussion and aid in visualizing and making concrete the more abstract concepts of risks and responses to them, a collaborative conceptual modeling activity can be implemented in the game. When **Team Risk** proposes their risk to humanity, they must create a simplified conceptual model of the risk with supplied pen and paper. When responding to the risk proposal, **Team Humanity** proceeds to model their response, and in the discussion phase, the models aid in explaining the complex interrelatedness of risks and responses.

The collaborative modeling exercise is enacted by following one of several possible reference conceptual models/ontologies/frameworks. For example, using a simplified model of climate change risk that represents *hazards*, *exposures* and *vulnerability* associated with the risk and derived from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) *Sixth Assessment Report* (AR6) definition of climate change risk [7, 8]. Alternatively, the impacts associated with the risks and responses can be modeled via the *social-ecological systems integrated model* [2, 3] or the conceptual model of the *common ontology of value and risk* (COVER) [5].

Some background and future developments

Risk Response was originally developed to elucidate the concepts of climate change risks and facilitate mitigation and adaptation discourse through collaborative modeling and debate by lay

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people as well as domain experts, in companion to related work [1] on an ontological unpacking of risk definitions proposed by the IPCC in the AR6 and Glossary.¹ Simplified risk scenarios were adapted for the game cards from the IPCC AR5 and AR6 reports, and associated literature from other international bodies, e.g. the *International Union for Conservation of Nature* (IUCN) [9] and the *Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services* (IPBES) [10]. These climate change-specific risks were then extended to include socio-technical and extraterrestrial risks, to demonstrate the interconnected nature of future social, ecological and technological change.

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¹ <https://apps.ipcc.ch/glossary/>

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